

The Influence of Financial Literacy on the Budgeting or Spending Behavior of Grade 12 ABM Students

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Abstract

Financial literacy is a critical competency for young adults navigating increasingly complex economic environments. This study evaluates the influence of financial literacy, specifically budgeting, saving and investing, and debt management, on the spending behavior of Grade 12 Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) students. Utilizing a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design, the study assessed 45 respondents regarding their financial proficiency and self-reported spending habits. The findings reveal that students possess a High level of financial literacy in budgeting and saving/investing knowledge, but only a Moderate understanding of debt management. In terms of behavior, respondents demonstrated a High level of responsible spending, particularly in prioritizing needs over wants and paying debts on time; however, a significant behavioral gap was identified in the Low frequency of tracking daily expenses, indicating a disconnect between theoretical planning and practical monitoring. Pearson correlation analysis confirmed a significant positive relationship between spending behavior and knowledge of both budgeting ($p < .05$) and saving ($p < .05$). Conversely, debt management knowledge showed no significant correlation with current spending practices ($p > .05$). The study concludes that while ABM students possess strong theoretical foundations in asset management which drive responsible spending, they lack depth in debt-related concepts and the practical discipline of expense monitoring. Recommendations include integrating experiential learning tools for expense tracking and intensifying instruction on credit and liability management within the ABM curriculum to bridge the gap between classroom concepts and real-world application.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Budgeting Behavior, Spending Behavior, ABM Students, Debt Management

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1. Introduction

Financial literacy has emerged as a critical competency for young individuals, involving the knowledge of financial concepts (such as budgeting, saving, investing, and debt) as well as the behaviors and attitudes needed to apply this understanding in decision-making (OECD, 2020). For senior high school students, especially those in the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand, financial literacy forms part of the foundational skills necessary for both academic success and future financial independence. As these students are being prepared for business- and finance-related careers, developing a strong level of financial literacy becomes even more vital.

Despite growing awareness of financial education, global assessments indicate that many students still exhibit low to moderate levels of financial competency. The OECD (2020) reported that many adolescents struggle to apply financial knowledge to real-world scenarios: in PISA assessments, around 20% of 15-year-olds score very low on tasks involving financial decision-making, and only about 31% reach levels sufficient for managing basic but meaningful financial tasks (e.g., bank accounts). The report also highlights that long-term financial decisions, such as taking on student loans, pose a risk of indebtedness later in life.

Recent studies in the Philippine context support these findings: for example, Saripada et al. (2024) found a significant relationship between financial literacy and spending habits among senior high school students. Another investigation by (Dela Rama et al., 2024; Gabay et al., 2024) reported that although SHS students generally understand financial knowledge, they struggle to apply it, particularly when managing debt and using borrowing (i.e., credit). Meanwhile, Daculan (2025) found that students' saving habits and spending practices vary significantly depending on their level of financial knowledge, indicating a strong link between literacy levels and financial behaviors.

Budgeting and spending behavior are central indicators of financial responsibility. Students who exhibit higher financial literacy tend to plan their budgets, track expenses, avoid impulsive buying, and demonstrate disciplined spending patterns (Mancone et al., 2024). Conversely, those with limited financial knowledge are more prone to overspending, accumulating unnecessary debt, or failing to save for future needs (Manipol & Pabelona, 2025). However, while financial literacy research has grown in recent years, there remains a lack of localized studies focusing specifically on the budgeting and spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students in the Philippine senior high school context.

Given these gaps, this study seeks to determine the influence of financial literacy on the budgeting and spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students. By understanding how financial knowledge relates to actual financial behavior, the study aims to provide evidence-based insights that can support schools, teachers, and policymakers in strengthening financial education programs for youth.

1.1. Conceptual Framework

Below, Figure 1, is a conceptual framework showing how financial literacy influences budgeting/spending behavior among Grade 12 ABM students.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

In the proposed framework, financial literacy is the primary independent variable, comprising three sub dimensions: budgeting knowledge, saving and investing knowledge, and debt management knowledge. These components are hypothesized to exert a positive influence on the budgeting and spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students, such that greater financial knowledge translates to more responsible financial practices. Empirical research supports this notion: for example, financial literacy has been linked to improved financial behavior among youth, including more disciplined saving and spending (Ablay et al., 2023). Altogether, this framework theorizes that financial literacy has impacts on spending practices and actual financial behavior to shape students’ budgeting and spending outcomes.

Recent studies among Philippine senior high school students have demonstrated that financial literacy – especially in saving, budgeting, and investing – significantly predicts financial behavior, including saving, spending habits, and financial goal setting (Pondang et al., 2024). In the Philippine context, a study among Carlos P. Garcia Senior High School students found a significant positive relationship between financial literacy and informed spending habits (Saripada et al., 2024). Similarly, a study in Gumaca, Quezon reported that financial literacy significantly predicts spending behavior and recommended integrating personal finance education into the senior high school curriculum (Vital et al., 2025). Meta-analytic evidence also indicates that financial literacy is a key predictor of financial behavior and overall financial well-being, underscoring the importance of equipping students with knowledge and skills to manage money effectively (Choowan et al., 2025). Based on these findings, the study proposes that financial literacy, operationalized through the subdimensions of budgeting knowledge, saving and investing knowledge, and debt management knowledge, influences the budgeting and spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students. To examine these relationships, descriptive statistics will summarize students’ financial literacy levels and spending behavior, while correlational and regression analyses will determine the strength and direction of the relationship between financial literacy components and budgeting/spending behavior. Validated questionnaires will be employed to measure financial literacy subdimensions and spending behavior, using Likert-scale items to capture students’ budgeting practices, saving tendencies, and responsible expenditure patterns.

2. Method

This study employed a quantitative descriptive–correlational research design to determine the influence of financial literacy on the budgeting or spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students. A descriptive approach was used to measure students’ levels of financial literacy and spending behavior, while the correlational design examined the relationships among the variables. This design is appropriate when the goal is to identify associations between measurable constructs without manipulating variables (Pondang et al., 2024; Daculan, 2025).

2.1. Research Respondents

The participants of the study were Grade 12 students enrolled in the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand at a public senior high school in one of the schools in Ozamiz City during School Year 2025–2026. A total of 45 respondents participated in the study. The sample size is consistent with recommended minimum requirements for correlational studies involving small populations (Fraenkel et al., 2022).

2.2. Research Instrument

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into two primary sections. The first section, the Financial Literacy Scale, assessed the respondents’ proficiency across three domains: budgeting knowledge, saving and investing knowledge, and debt management knowledge. The second section, the Budgeting or Spending Behavior Scale, evaluated the students’ spending discipline, budgeting habits, and financial decision-making. To ensure instrument validity, the items for both scales were adapted from established financial literacy and behavior instruments utilized in recent research by Vieira et al. (2020).

2.3. Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure commenced with securing formal approval from the school principal and research coordinator. In strict adherence to ethical guidelines for studies involving minors (APA, 2020) and DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016, necessary parental consent and student assent were obtained prior to participation. Subsequently, the adopted questionnaires were administered during designated class periods. To guarantee anonymity and confidentiality, respondents were instructed to refrain from writing their names on the instruments. Once the students completed the survey, the questionnaires were retrieved and carefully checked for completeness before the data were encoded into statistical software for analysis.

2.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, median, and standard deviation) were used to summarize students’ levels of financial literacy and spending behavior. To determine the relationship between financial literacy components and budgeting/spending behavior, Pearson’s correlation coefficient was utilized, as the data met normality assumptions. Interpretation of correlation strengths followed conventional statistical guidelines. The significance level was set at $\alpha = .05$ (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

2.5. Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards by ensuring voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent. Respondents were assured that their answers would be used solely for academic purposes and reported in aggregate form to protect identities. Data were stored securely and will be disposed of according to institutional guidelines.

2.6. AI Use Statement

This study utilized AI-assisted tools, specifically OpenAI's ChatGPT, to support the development of selected research components such as generating initial drafts of the introduction, conceptual framework, and methodological descriptions. The researcher reviewed, validated, edited, and refined all AI-generated content to ensure accuracy, contextual relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. The use of ChatGPT was limited to enhancing clarity and organization of written sections; it did not perform data collection, statistical analysis, interpretation of findings, or draw conclusions, which remained solely the researcher's responsibility.

AI tools such as ChatGPT are increasingly recognized for their usefulness in improving academic writing efficiency, organization, and idea generation, provided that human oversight and verification remain central to the research process (Kung et al., 2023; Zhang, 2025). The integration of AI in this study adhered to ethical standards by maintaining transparency, accuracy, and academic integrity throughout the research process.

3. Results

3.1. Level of Financial Literacy of Grade 12 ABM Students

The study assessed financial literacy across three components: budgeting knowledge, saving and investing knowledge, and debt management knowledge.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the three components of financial literacy assessed among Grade 12 ABM students: budgeting knowledge, saving and investing knowledge, and debt management knowledge.

Table 1. Financial Literacy Level of Grade 12 ABM

Component	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	Interpretation
Budgeting Knowledge	45	26.32	6.45	High
Saving & Investing Knowledge	45	26.29	6.83	High
Debt Management Knowledge	45	21.62	8.29	Moderate

Scale Range and Verbal Interpretations:

<i>Average scores</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
22.01-30.00	High	Demonstrates strong financial literacy and understanding of concepts.
15.01-22.00	Moderate	Shows adequate understanding but may need improvement in some areas.
7.01-15.00	Low	Possesses limited financial literacy; requires further learning and practice.
0.00-7.00	Very Low	Possesses limited financial literacy; requires further learning and practice.

As shown in Table 1, the respondents demonstrated a High level of literacy in two of the three domains. Budgeting Knowledge obtained the highest mean score ($M = 26.32$, $SD = 6.45$), closely followed by Saving and Investing Knowledge ($M = 26.29$, $SD = 6.83$). These scores fall within the 22.01–30.00 range, indicating that students possess a strong understanding of concepts related to planning expenses and accumulating assets.

In contrast, Debt Management Knowledge received the lowest mean score of 21.62 ($SD = 8.29$). This score falls within the 15.01–22.00 range, corresponding to a Moderate interpretation. Additionally, the standard deviation for Debt Management ($SD = 8.29$) is higher than that of the other two components, suggesting a wider variability in students' understanding of debt-related concepts compared to their knowledge of budgeting and saving.

3.2. Level of Budgeting or Spending Behavior

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics for the spending behavior of the Grade 12 ABM students. The data reveals the specific financial habits practiced by the respondents, ranging from budgeting allowances to tracking expenses.

Table 2. *Spending Behavior of Grade 12 ABM*

<i>N</i>	Mean	Median	<i>SD</i>	Interpretation
45	3.79	3.78	0.299	High

<i>Scale Range and Verbal Interpretation</i>		<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Range</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	
4.21 – 5.00	Very High	<i>Demonstrates excellent and responsible spending behavior.</i>
3.41 – 4.20	High	<i>Shows good spending behavior; students are generally careful and disciplined with their expenses.</i>
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	<i>Displays average spending behavior; sometimes responsible but may overspend occasionally.</i>
1.81 – 2.60	Low	<i>Indicates poor spending habits and limited financial control.</i>
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	<i>Shows very poor spending behavior; highly impulsive and unplanned spending.</i>

Table 2 result indicates that, on average, the Grade 12 ABM students have a high level of spending behavior (mean = 3.79 on a 5-point scale). Given the scale interpretation (3.41–4.20 = “High”), this suggests that these students are generally careful and disciplined with their expenses. In other words, they are not spending recklessly; rather, they show fairly mature financial habits relative to their peers. This is a promising baseline, because it suggests that ABM students, who are presumably more exposed to business and finance education, are not inherently impulsive spenders, but may already have developed a degree of self-regulation in their monetary behavior.

3.3. Relationship Between Financial Literacy and Spending Behavior

Table 3 presents the results of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r) analysis used to determine the significant relationship between the students' financial literacy domains and their spending behavior.

Table 3. Correlation Results

Financial Literacy Component	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Budgeting Knowledge → Spending Behavior	.387	.009	Moderate positive, significant
Saving & Investing Knowledge → Spending Behavior	.333	.025	Moderate positive, significant
Debt Management Knowledge → Spending Behavior	.156	.308	Weak positive, not significant

As shown in Table 3, the analysis reveals varying degrees of relationship between the variables. A moderate positive correlation was found between Budgeting Knowledge and spending behavior ($r = .387$). The calculated p -value of .009 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that as students' knowledge of budgeting increases, their responsible spending behavior also improves significantly.

Similarly, a moderate positive correlation was observed between Saving and Investing Knowledge and spending behavior ($r = .333$). With a p -value of .025, the relationship is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that students who are more knowledgeable about saving and investing tend to exhibit better spending habits.

In contrast, the relationship between Debt Management Knowledge and spending behavior yielded a low positive correlation ($r = .156$). However, the computed p -value of .308 is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis for this variable. This implies that among these respondents, knowledge of debt management does not have a statistically significant influence on their current spending behavior.

3.4. Summary of Results

The descriptive analysis reveals that the respondents possess a generally High level of financial literacy, specifically excelling in Budgeting Knowledge and Saving and Investing Knowledge. However, a distinct gap exists in Debt Management Knowledge, which was rated only as Moderate and exhibited higher variability among students. In terms of financial habits, the students demonstrated a High level of responsible spending behavior, characterizing them as disciplined and careful with their expenses. The inferential analysis confirms that this positive behavior is significantly linked to their understanding of budgeting and saving concepts, as evidenced by the moderate positive correlations found. Conversely, the study established that knowledge of debt management does not significantly influence current spending habits, suggesting that this specific domain of literacy remains theoretically detached from the daily financial decisions of the students.

4. Discussion

4.1. Financial Literacy Status of ABM Students

The assessment of financial literacy among Grade 12 ABM students revealed a distinct dichotomy in their knowledge base. The respondents demonstrated a High level of proficiency in Budgeting Knowledge and Saving and Investing Knowledge. This aligns with

the findings of Templa et al. (2025), who observed that students exposed to specialized business curricula often exhibit superior understanding of asset accumulation and expense planning compared to their non-ABM peers. This high proficiency suggests that the ABM strand effectively transfers theoretical concepts related to wealth generation and resource allocation. However, a critical gap emerged in Debt Management Knowledge, which was rated only as Moderate and displayed the highest variability among respondents. This finding corroborates the work of Artavanis and Karra (2020), who warn that while students may understand how to save, they often lack the sophisticated understanding of credit mechanisms, interest rates, and liability management. The lower score in this domain implies that current educational interventions may be heavily weighted toward asset management while inadvertently underemphasizing the risks and mechanics of borrowing, leaving students potentially vulnerable to future financial mismanagement.

4.2. Level of Spending Behavior

In terms of actual financial conduct, the Grade 12 ABM students exhibited a High level of responsible spending behavior. With a mean score indicating that students are generally careful and disciplined, these results resonate with Vital et al. (2025), who noted that senior high school students in private institutions often display positive spending habits driven by their academic environment and parental socialization. The data suggests that these students are not impulsive; rather, they have developed a degree of self-regulation that allows them to prioritize needs and manage their allowances effectively. However, a significant behavioral disconnect was identified: the practice of tracking daily expenses was rated as Low. This phenomenon highlights a gap between attitude and action; while students value financial discipline conceptually, they lack the technical habit of recording transactions. Hasanudin et al. (2022) note that without the reinforcement of monitoring tools (like ledgers or apps), high "financial maturity" can remain fragile, as unmonitored small expenses can easily undermine a mental budget.

4.3. The Relationship Between Literacy and Behavior

Further analysis confirmed that financial knowledge serves as a significant predictor for behavior, though this relationship is domain-specific. The study established a significant, moderate positive relationship between spending behavior and the domains of Budgeting and Saving/Investing Knowledge. This indicates that as students gain a deeper understanding of how to plan and save, their actual spending habits improve. This supports the "knowledge-behavior" link described by LeBaron et al. (2019), positing that cognitive competence in finance provides the necessary toolkit for making rational consumption choices. Conversely, a notable anomaly was observed regarding Debt Management, which showed no significant relationship with spending behavior. This disconnect can be interpreted through the lens of situational relevance. As O'Connell (2008) suggests, financial knowledge impacts behavior most effectively when it is immediately applicable. Since high school students primarily operate on cash allowances and rarely engage in formal borrowing, their theoretical knowledge of debt—whether high or moderate—remains "inert" and does not currently influence their daily spending decisions.

4.4. Implications for Financial Education

These findings underscore a specific need to recalibrate financial education strategies. While the current curriculum succeeds in fostering saving and budgeting skills, the moderate proficiency in debt management is a concern for the students' transition to adulthood. As Elliott and Beverly (2011) emphasize, comprehensive financial capability requires not just the ability to save, but the foresight to manage liabilities. Consequently, to promote a more holistic financial literacy, educational interventions must move beyond the "savings-centric" model to include rigorous, practical training on debt management, ensuring that students are as competent in handling credit as they are in managing assets.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

The study concludes that Grade 12 ABM students possess a high level of financial literacy in budgeting and saving, which significantly correlates with and positively influences their responsible spending behavior. However, a distinct gap exists in debt management knowledge, which remains at a moderate level and shows no statistical relationship with their current financial habits. This suggests that while students are proficient in planning and resource allocation, their understanding of debt is less developed and currently detached from their daily financial decisions, highlighting a specific area where the curriculum and instruction require strengthening to ensure holistic financial capability.

5.1.1. Limitations of the Study

While this study offers valuable insights into the financial behavior of ABM students, it has limitations that temper its conclusions. First, the sample size was relatively small ($N = 45$) and limited to a single school, which may not be fully representative of the entire Grade 12 ABM population in the Philippines. Consequently, the generalizability of the findings is limited. Second, the cross-sectional design prohibits causal inference, meaning the study can describe relationships but not definitively prove that financial literacy causes specific spending behaviors. Finally, the reliance on self-reported data may reflect students' perceived rather than actual financial habits. Future research should employ larger, stratified samples across multiple schools to increase generalizability and include behavioral measures (such as spending records or simulated tasks) to validate these findings.

5.2. Recommendations to Improve Financial Literacy

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, particularly the identified gap in debt management knowledge, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the financial literacy and spending behavior of Grade 12 ABM students:

5.2.1. Integrate Practical Financial Education Activities

The school should incorporate applied financial learning experiences—such as personal budgeting exercises, stock market simulations, and case studies—into the ABM curriculum. Research indicates that experiential learning significantly improves students' ability to connect theory with practice, leading to better financial decision-making skills than traditional instruction alone (Pichop, 2025). These activities will allow students to apply

budgeting, saving, and investing concepts in realistic scenarios, thereby reinforcing their competencies.

5.2.2. Conduct Financial Literacy Seminars and Workshops

Regular financial literacy seminars should be conducted in collaboration with banks, financial experts, or local business professionals. These programs should emphasize responsible borrowing, the proper use of credit, and debt management strategies. Studies suggest that targeted financial management programs in educational institutions are positively correlated with responsible spending and saving habits among students (Halawa et al., 2022). Exposure to real-life financial scenarios through these experts can help students develop a deeper, practical understanding of managing money wisely.

5.2.3. Promote Savings and Investment Programs for Students

Schools may initiate or partner with financial institutions to create student savings programs or financial literacy clubs. Access to savings accounts and financial education at a young age is linked to improved financial capability and asset accumulation (Elliott & Beverly, 2011). These initiatives encourage students to cultivate the habit of saving early, plan for future financial goals, and gain basic exposure to investment opportunities that promote long-term financial independence.

5.2.4. Integrate Debt Management Lessons into Business-Related Subjects

Teachers handling ABM subjects—such as Organization and Management, Business Finance, or Principles of Marketing—should explicitly include lessons focused on credit use, interest rates, loan repayment, and financial responsibility. Artavanis and Karra (2020) found that students with lower financial literacy are significantly more likely to underestimate future loan payments and struggle with debt repayment. Integrating these topics into existing subjects ensures that students receive continuous reinforcement of debt management principles, addressing the specific weakness identified in this study.

5.2.5. Encourage Parental and Community Involvement

Schools should collaborate with parents and community organizations to promote financial literacy beyond the classroom. Parents are often the primary source of financial socialization for children; thus, encouraging them to involve their children in household budgeting and expense discussions can be highly effective. Overt financial education at home, such as discussing credit and debt, has been associated with healthier financial behaviors and lower debt accumulation in emerging adulthood (LeBaron et al., 2018).

5.2.6. Monitor and Evaluate Financial Literacy Programs

A regular assessment and evaluation system should be established to measure the effectiveness of financial literacy initiatives implemented in the school. Continuous evaluation allows educators to identify gaps in understanding and adjust instructional strategies accordingly, ensuring the programs remain relevant and effective in improving students' financial competencies (O'Connell, 2008).

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References

1. Ablay, J. A. M. C., L. Gindap, R. A., L. Ralla, P. J., P. Garcia, N. P., P. Garcia, N. P., Pacete, D. A. B., Raminto, P. N., S. Sayon, S. K., & Tomaquin, R. G. (2023). The Relationship between Spending Behavior and Student Financial Management Skills. *International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.54476/ioer-imrj/579933>
2. Artavanis, N., & Karra, S. (2020). Financial literacy and student debt. *The European Journal of Finance*, 26(4-5), 382-401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1351847x.2019.1711435>
3. Carvajal, W., Baltonado, C., Gocela, M., Pajes, L., Soliman, A., Bankas, H., Lubon, C. F., & Albano, M. E. (2025). Level of Financial Literacy and Debt Management: Basis for Personal Financial Management Program. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 41(2), 206-215. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj.410203>
4. Choowan, P., Daovisan, H., & Suwanwong, C. (2024). Effects of financial literacy and financial behavior on financial well-being: Meta-analytical review of experimental studies. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 13(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs13010001>
5. Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications. <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/research-design/book270550>
6. Daculan, A. G. (2025). Financial knowledge, saving habits and spending habits among fourth year students in the University of Eastern Philippines College of Education. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 19(9), 74-92. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajarr/2025/v19i91143>
7. Dela Rama, K. A., Baylon, F., Balwet, L. F., Pullos, K. E., Durias, R. C., Cabusca, J. F., Eguia, A. L., Cabilin, L. M., Duran, R., Mante, J., Prepecio, D., Gilongos, C. J., & Rosel, M. (2024, July 31). Assessing the financial literacy of senior high school and college students: A comprehensive analysis. *The Threshold*, 16(1). https://www.jrmsu.university/index.php/The_Threshold/article/view/11
8. DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016 - Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda. Department of Education Republic of the Philippines. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_039.pdf
9. Elliott, W., & Beverly, S. G. (2011). The role of savings and wealth in reducing "wilt" between expectations and college attendance. *Journal of Children and Poverty*, 17(2), 165-185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10796126.2011.538375>
10. Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2022). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (10th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education. <https://saochhengpheng.wordpress.com/wp->

content/uploads/2017/03/jack_fraenkel_norman_wallen_helen_hyun-how_to_design_and_evaluate_research_in_education_8th_edition_-mcgraw-hill_humanities_social_sciences_languages2011.pdf

11. Frees, D., Gangal, A., & Shaviro, C. (2024). *Quantifying the causal effect of financial literacy courses on financial health*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.01789>
12. Gabay, P. J. V., Bagsic, A. E. G., Lauresta, C. J., Vetuz, M. M., & Beri, J. C. E. (2024). Financial literacy among the senior high school students: Basis for financial stewardship plan. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 10(3), 01-12. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijaems.103.1>
13. Halawa, E., Bate'e, M. M., Bu'ulolo, N. A., & Aferiaman Telaumbanua. (2024). The Effect of Financial Literacy on the Financial Management of Students. *Golden Ratio of Data in Summary*, 4(2), 473–481. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grdis.v4i2.569>
14. Kung, T. H., Cheatham, M., Medenilla, A., Sillos, C., De Leon, L., Elepaño, C., Madriaga, M., Aggabao, R., Diaz-Candido, G., Maningo, J., & Tseng, V. (2023). Performance of ChatGPT on USMLE: Potential for AI-assisted medical education using large language models. *PLOS Digital Health*, 2(2), e0000198. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000198>
15. LeBaron, A. B., Runyan, S. D., Jorgensen, B. L., Marks, L. D., Li, X., & Hill, E. J. (2018). Practice Makes Perfect: Experiential Learning as a Method for Financial Socialization. *Journal of Family Issues*, 40(4), 435–463. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X18812917>
16. Mancone, S., Tosti, B., Corrado, S., Spica, G., Zanon, A., & Diotaiuti, P. (2024). Youth, money, and behavior: the impact of financial literacy programs. *Frontiers in Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1397060>
17. Manipol, V. S., & Pabelona, R. B. (2025). Unraveling the Nexus: Exploring the Interplay of Financial Literacy, Behavior and Practices. *TEM Journal*, 14(3), 2124–2133. <https://doi.org/10.18421/tem143-19>
18. O'Connell, A. (2008). Evaluating the effectiveness of financial education programmes. *OECD Journal: General Papers Special Issue: Financial Education*, 2008(3). https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2009/02/oecd-journal-general-papers-volume-2008-issue-3_glgh88eb/gen_papers-v2008-3-en.pdf
19. OECD. (2020). *PISA 2018 results: Financial literacy* (Vol. IV). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/48ebd1ba-en>
20. Pichop, G. N. (2025). Integrating the Stock Market Simulation Into the Core Curriculum of a Business Program: Evidence of the Impact on Learning From a Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 27(1). <https://doi.org/10.33423/jabe.v27i1.7503>
21. Pondang, K., Saripada, N. A., Balindong, F. A. M., & Pailan, M. G. (2024). Financial literacy and spending habits among senior high school students. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 6(5), 8403–8407. <https://doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS57904>

22. Rodriguez, J. M., Labong, D. C., & Palallos, L. (2024). The Mediation of Financial Behavior to Financial Literacy and Spending Habits of Gen Z: An Exploratory Factor Analysis. *Journal of Global Awareness*, 5(2), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.24073/jga/5/02/05>
23. Rosit, J. X. G., Bancal, D. H. A., Baraquil, K. E. M., Bongabong, R. M. R., Fernandez, J. S. M., Mamales, G. M. T., Ortiliano, E. Jr, Sabillano, M. S., Torregoza, S. G., Undalayan, S. L. G., Clamares, K. J. M., & Pelandas, A. M. O. (2024). Family Involvement and Saving and Spending Behaviours as Predictors to Financial Literacy of Senior High School Students: A Quantitative Investigation. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(4), 2430–2440. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/bcp/journal/v8y2024i4p2430-2440.html>
24. Saripada, N. S., Balindong, F. A. M., Pailan, M. G. C., Dalipe, M. R. P., Tuazon, M. B. F., & Pondang, K. A. (2024). Financial literacy and spending habits among senior high school students. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering, Technology and Science*, 6(5), 8403–8407. https://www.irjmet.com/uploadedfiles/paper//issue_5_may_2024/57904/final/fin_irj_mets1716917753.pdf
25. Templa, E. L., Andea, R. Jr. B., Bagahansol, J. D. M., Carreon, R. B., Comendador, L. G., Labrador, J. G., Miscreola, D. J. V., Tapay, A. J. D., & Uson, P. G. R. A. (2025). The influence of financial literacy on the budgeting practices among college students in a private Catholic school: Input for student literacy program. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 38(8), 959–973. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj.380810>
26. Vieira, K. M., Moreira Júnior, F. de J., & Potrich, A. C. G. (2020). Measuring financial literacy: proposition of an instrument based on the Item Response Theory. *Ciência E Natura*, 42, e38. <https://doi.org/10.5902/2179460X39864>
27. Vital, J., Oreta, M., Espiritu, M., Ramos, R., & Ramos, S. (2025). Effects of Financial Literacy to the Spending Habits of Selected Senior High School Students in a Private Institution in Gumaca, Quezon. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 41(10), 1155–1168. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj.411006>
28. Zhang, K. (2025). Enhancing critical writing through AI feedback: A randomized control study. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(5), Article 600. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15050600>